

**List of Artworks Depicting the British Historic Environment during the Second
World War**

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The following artworks were viewed by the author while preparing Chapter 4 of his doctoral thesis. Works in bold are known to have been part of the War Artists' Advisory Committee collection. Works depicting locations outside Britain, fully imaginary scenes, or architecture not known to be historically significant are listed in a separate section at the end of this list. The list also includes several works from the pre- and postwar years.

Allen, Kathleen. *The Last Bus*. 1945. Oil on canvas. 76.2 x 55.9 cm. Leamington Spa Art Gallery and Museum, LEAMG : A944/2000.
<https://www.search.windowsonwarwickshire.org.uk/Details.aspx?&ResourceID=24495>.

Armstrong, John. ***Coggeshall Church, Essex***. 1940. Tempera on wood. 57.1 x 38.1 cm. Tate, N05675.
<https://www.tate.org.uk/art/artworks/armstrong-coggeshall-church-essex-n05675>.

Artist unknown. *St Mary-le-Port Church and Street, Showing Bomb Damage*. 1941. Drawing, watercolour. Bristol Museums Collections, K6237.
<https://collections.bristolmuseums.org.uk/collections/c9e6bb08-20c0-38d8-8807-0dfce11c993e/>.

Artist unknown. *Palace of Westminster at Night*. 1941. Watercolour on paper. 71.7 x 53.9 cm. Parliamentary Art Collection, London, WOA 2673.
https://heritagecollections.parliament.uk/collections/getrecord/HOP_WOA_2673.

Atkinson, Leslie. *All Saints Chapel, Bath, after the Blitz*. 1942. 58.5 x 95. In Wyatt, Richard. "Those Wartime Years Remembered." *Bath Newseum* (blog), June 3, 2019.
<https://bathnewseum.com/2019/06/03/those-wartime-years-remembered/>.

Atkinson, Leslie. *Julian Road, Bath, after the Blitz*. 1942. 52.1 x 88.2 cm. In Bath Echo News Team. "Victoria Art Gallery Exhibition to Showcase Outstanding 1940s Artwork." *Bath Echo*, June 4, 2019.
<https://www.bathecho.co.uk/news/community/victoria-art-gallery-showcase-artwork-1940s-84562/>.

Atkinson, Leslie. *Lansdown Place East after the Blitz*. In *Repairing War Torn Bath*. Bath: Bath Preservation Trust, 2005, figure 11. Catalogue for an exhibition at the Bath Preservation Trust, Bath, 1 – 25 November 2005.
<https://museumofbatharchitecture.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/4e.2-Reparing-War-Torn-Bath-2005.pdf>.

Atkinson, Leslie. *Somerset Place*. 1942. In *Repairing War Torn Bath*. Bath: Bath Preservation Trust, 2005, figure 6. Catalogue for an exhibition at the Bath Preservation Trust, Bath, 1 – 25 November 2005.
<https://museumofbatharchitecture.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/4e.2-Reparing-War-Torn-Bath-2005.pdf>.

Atkinson, Leslie. *St Andrew's Church, Julian Road, Bath*. 1942.
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5c8d4de47980b37c2a5e38fa/t/5ca745d3f9619a75aae5047b/1554466264384/War+Artists+on+Lansdown.pdf>.

Austin, Robert. *Our Heritage: Winston Churchill*. 1943. Lithograph. 64.2 x 50.8 cm. In Llewellyn, Sacha and Paul Liss, eds. *WW II: War Pictures by British Artists*. London: Liss Llewellyn Fine Art, 2016, 164–165.

Baker, Gladys. *Destruction at Holborn Viaduct – City Temple and St Andrew's, Holborn*. c. 1941. Oil on canvas board. Royal Air Force Museum, UK, X002-9642.
<https://collections.rafmuseum.org.uk/collection/object/object-104485/>.

Barry, Claude Francis. *The Heart of the Empire: Our Finest Hour, 1940*. 1940. Oil on canvas. 109 x 269 cm. Liss Llewellyn Fine Art, SKU 587.
<https://lissllewellyn.com/product/the-heart-of-the-empire-our-finest-hour-1940/>.

Barry, Claude Francis. *Houses of Parliament – A Wartime Nocturne*. 1941. Oil on canvas. 75 x 96 cm. Sold by Mutual Art.
<https://www.mutualart.com/Artwork/Houses-of-Parliament---a-wartime-Nocturn/9A95D5E3D6815773>.

Barry, Claude Francis. *London Blitz*. 1940. Oil on canvas. 90 x 90 cm. In Llewellyn, Sacha and Paul Liss, eds. *WW II: War Pictures by British Artists*. London: Liss Llewellyn Fine Art, 2016, 64.

Barry, Claude Francis. *Tower Bridge, London: A War-Time Nocturne*. n.d. Oil on canvas. 73 x 94.5 cm. Museum and Art Swindon, AG86.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/tower-bridge-london-a-war-time-nocturne-64517>.

Barry, Claude Francis. *V. E. Day, London*. 1945. Oil on canvas. 137.2 x 172.8 cm. Sold by Mutual Art.
<https://www.mutualart.com/Artwork/V-E--Day--London/B60E831748581BCF>.

Barry, Claude Francis. *Windsor Castle and Wartime Nocturne*. Oil on canvas. 65 x 81 cm. In Campbell, Katie. *Moon behind Clouds: An Introduction to the Life and Work of Sir Claude Francis Barry 1883–1970*. St Helier, Jersey: Fine Art Promotions, 1999, 80.
<https://archive.org/details/moonbehindclouds0000kati/page/80/mode/2up?q=windsor>.

Bayes, Walter. *Battle of Britain: Parachutists from an Enemy Aircraft Brought down in an Apparent Attempt to Bomb Buckingham Palace*. 1942. Oil on canvas. 119 x 140.9 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 2514.
<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/1880>,
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/battle-of-britain-parachutists-from-an-enemy-aircraft-brought-down-in-an-apparent-attempt-to-bomb-buckingham-palace-7071>.

Benner, William. *After the Blitz, near Trivett's Works from Cliff Road, Nottingham*. 1941. Oil on canvas. 48.3 x 38.1 cm. Nottingham City Museums and Galleries, NCM 1943-2.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/after-the-blitz-near-trivetts-works-from-cliff-road-nottingham-47288>.

Beresford, Frank Ernest. *Demolition of the Blitzed House of Commons*. 1945. Oil on canvas. 86.5 x 99 cm. Parliamentary Art Collection, London, WOA 7395.
https://heritagecollections.parliament.uk/collections/getrecord/HOP_WOA_7395,
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/demolition-of-the-blitzed-house-of-commons-231263/>.

Beresford, Frank Ernest. *A Hurricane at the Guildhall, London*. 1943. Oil on canvas. 51 x 61 cm. Guildhall Art Gallery, 1579.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/a-hurricane-at-the-guildhall-london-51386/>.

Best, Gladys. *Site of Bedford Circus, Exeter, which had been Cleared Following the Bombing of 1942 (looking towards Southernhay Church)*. 1942. Watercolour. 28 x 40 cm. Royal Albert Memorial Museum and Art Gallery, Exeter, 65/2023.
<https://rammcollections.org.uk/collections/c4ae774e-39b6-3fd8-94fd-96ab80f24ffb/>.

Bomberg, David. *Evening in the City of London*. 1944. Charcoal drawing. 46.4 x 59 cm. Ashmolean Museum, University of Oxford, WA1981.606.
<https://www.ashmolean.org/collections-online#/item/ash-object-95970>.

Bomberg, David. *Evening in the City of London*. 1944. Oil on canvas. 86.5 x 106.8 cm. London Museum, 85.219.
<https://www.londonmuseum.org.uk/collections/v/object-102272/evening-in-the-city-of-london/>.

Bone, Muirhead. *The Exeter and Ajax Parade, 1940* [taking place at Horse Guards Parade, London]. 1940. Chalk, ink and wash on paper. 51.5 x 93 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 311.
<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/3019>.

Bone, Muirhead. *Ruins of Coventry Cathedral*. 1944. Pastel, charcoal, watercolour and ink on paper. 132 x 79 cm. The Herbert Art Gallery and Museum, Coventry. Art Fund.
<https://www.artfund.org/our-purpose/art-funded-by-you/coventry-cathedral-ruins>.

Bone, Muirhead. *St Bride's and the City after the Fire, 29 December 1940*. 1941. Chalk and ink on paper. 197.8 x 112 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 1076.
<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/3028>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Central Criminal Court*. 1945. Pastel on paper. 23 x 30 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25064, q8040039.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22834>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Central Criminal Court* [view from Paternoster Row]. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 23 x 29 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25071, q8039912.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22841>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Christ Church*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 25 x 35 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25084, q2825532.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22854>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Christ Church, Newgate Street*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 20 x 24 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25063, q2825549.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22833>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *City Temple* [with Holborn Viaduct]. 1945. Crayon and watercolour on paper. 25 x 17 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24963, q6012990.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22735>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Farringdon Street*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 27 x 35 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25107, q4026249.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22877>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Foster Lane* [St Paul's and St Vedast in background]. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 17 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24955, p5351750.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22727>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Great St Helens*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 14 x 20 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24956, q4770752.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22728>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Great Tower Street* [All Hallows Barking (by the Tower) and Trinity House]. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 21 x 27 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24957, v9014340.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22729>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Guildhall* [view from Fore Street]. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 35 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25110, q4921116.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22880>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Guildhall* [view from Guildhall Yard]. 1941. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 23 x 31 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25086, q4921085.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22856>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Ludgate Hill* [with St Martin within Ludgate]. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 15 x 24 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24959, q8019594.

<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22731>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Public Record Office*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 16 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25142, q2823102.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22911>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Ruins around St Paul's*. 1945. Oil on canvas. 71 x 86 cm. Guildhall Art Gallery. London Picture Archive, 11999, 1910.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=10300>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Alban and St Mary Aldermanbury*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 24 x 35 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25111, v8482725.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22881>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Andrew, Holborn*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 20 x 26 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25135, v9010520.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22904>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Bartholomews Priory*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 17 x 12 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25068, v9042419.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22838>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Bride*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 18 x 26 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25136, q2322334.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22905>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Giles without Cripplegate*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 15 x 24 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25069, q4769016.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22839>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Giles without Cripplegate* [from Milton Street]. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 24 x 33 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25108, q476900x.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22878>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Lawrence Jewry*. 1941. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 21 x 28 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25070, q6060517.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22840>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Martin-in-the-Fields*. 1945. Pastel, pencil and watercolour on paper. 29 x 21 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25072, p540466x.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22842>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Mary Aldermanbury*. 1945. Pencil and watercolour on paper. 18 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25139, q8020924.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22908>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Mary le Bow*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 31 x 22 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25104, q771097x.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22874>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Michael Paternoster Royal*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 25 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24954, q802009x.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22726>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Nicholas Cole Abbey*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 14 x 21 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25138, q803676x.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22907>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Nicholas Cole Abbey* [from Nighridger Street]. 1945. Pencil and watercolour on paper. 20 x 27 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25067, q8036888.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22837>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Olave, Hart Street*. 1945. Pastel on paper. 41 x 29 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25145, q8036411.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22914>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Paul's Cathedral* [looking south from Ivy Lane]. 1945. Pencil and watercolour on paper. 19 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25065, q8024187.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22835>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Paul's Cathedral* [view from Holborn]. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 25 x 35 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25109, q6011648.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22879>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Paul's Cathedral* [view from Paternoster Row]. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 28 x 34 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25106, q8024543.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22876>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Paul's Cathedral* [view from the east]. 1945.. Pastel on paper. 25 x 31 cm The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25090, q8024307.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22860>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Paul's Churchyard*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 24 x 17 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24962, v848285x.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22734>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Stephens, Walbrook*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 35 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25088, p5358746.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22858>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *St Vedast*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 27 cm x 20 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25141, p5351744.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22910>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Temple Church*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 23 x 33 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25091, p5357563.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22861>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *War Damage [London Wall and Fore Street]*. 1945. Pastel and watercolour on paper. 20 x 30 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25134, q4766940.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22903>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *War Damage, Tower Hill [The Tiger Tavern]*. 1945. Pencil and watercolour on paper. 26 x 36 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25113, p7490651.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22883>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *War Damage [view of Holborn Viaduct area]*. 1945. Pastel, pencil and watercolour on paper. 15 cm x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25140, q6013009.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22909>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *War Damage [view of Moorgate area, north of Fore Street]*. 1945. Pastel, pencil and watercolour on paper. 24 x 35 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25144, q4766957.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22913>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *War Damage [view of St James Garlickhythe and St Michael Paternoster Royal]*. 1945. Pencil and watercolour on paper. 25 x 36 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 25143, q2323701.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22912>.

Borough Johnson, Ernest. *Watling Street [with St Mary Aldermary]*. 1945. Watercolour on paper. 16 x 25 cm. The London Archives. London Picture Archive, 24960, q7714151.
<https://www.londonpicturearchive.org.uk/view-item?i=22732>.

Boussemaere, P. *East End and Docks, Bombed, 1940*. c. 1941. Oil on hardboard. 53.9 x 68.5 cm. Royal Air Force Museum, UK, FA04327.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/east-end-and-docks-bombed-1940-135676/>.

Bown, Albert Charles. *Bedford Circus after the Blitz*. 1942–43. Watercolour (?). 24.5 x 34.5 cm. Royal Albert Memorial Museum and Art Gallery, Exeter, 57/1948/3.
<https://rammcollections.org.uk/collections/e63c843d-dada-3672-8ef5-79cae014f140/>.

Bowyer, Beryl Clifton. *Bayley Lane and the Ruined East End of St Michael's, Coventry*. 1942. Oil on canvas laid on board. 25.4 x 40.4 cm. Herbert Art Gallery and Museum, Coventry, VA.2003.5.10.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/bayley-lane-and-the-ruined-east-end-of-st-michaels-coventry-55408>.

Bowyer, Beryl Clifton. *Holy Trinity, Coventry*. 1942. Oil on canvas. 45.7 x 30.5 cm. Herbert Art Gallery and Museum, Coventry, VA.2003.5.03.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/holy-trinity-coventry-55400/>.

Bowyer, Beryl Clifton. *Holy Trinity, Coventry*. 1943. Oil on canvas laid on board. 45.3 x 30 cm. Herbert Art Gallery and Museum, Coventry, VA.2003.5.02.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/holy-trinity-coventry-55399/>.

Bowyer, Beryl Clifton. *The Ruins of St Michael's Baptist Church, the 'Golden Cross' Inn and the Law Courts, Coventry*. 1942–43. Oil on canvas laid on board. 25 x 35.3 cm. Herbert Art Gallery and Museum, Coventry, VA.2003.5.11.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/the-ruins-of-st-michaels-baptist-church-the-golden-cross-inn-and-the-law-courts-coventry-55409>.

Bowyer, Beryl Clifton. *Street Scene with Ruined Market Tower, Coventry*. 1941. Oil on canvas laid on board. 36.5 x 51.6 cm. Herbert Art Gallery and Museum, Coventry, VA.2003.5.08.
<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/street-scene-with-ruined-market-tower-coventry-55405>.

Bull, Norma. *The Bomb Disposal Service at the Circus, Bath*. 1942. 39.5 x 52.8 cm. "Victoria Gallery Hosts Blitzed! War Artists in Bath." *BBC Home*, 24 September 2014.
https://www.bbc.co.uk/somerset/content/articles/2005/05/05/blitzed_event_feature.shtml.

Bull, Norma. *Bow Church from Bread Street*. 1941. Pencil with watercolour. 23 x 19 cm. Castlemaine Art Museum, Castlemaine, Australia, G620.
<https://collection.castlemaineartmuseum.org.au/objects/620/bow-church-from-bread-street>.
At the time of writing, the image for *Bow Church from Bread Street* has been mixed up with Bull's *A Chelsea Incident*, G619, <https://collection.castlemaineartmuseum.org.au/objects/619/a-chelsea-incident>.

Bull, Norma. *Bristol's Floating Harbour*. 1943. Drawing in pencil, pen, black ink, watercolour. 44.8 x 57.6 cm. National Gallery of Australia, Canberra, 84.1717, IRN 90665.
<https://searchthecollection.nga.gov.au/object/90665>.

Bull, Norma. *The Chelsea Royal Hospital Infirmary, as Destroyed by Enemy Action*. 1941. Drawing, watercolour. Royal Collection Trust, RCIN 453416.

<https://www.rct.uk/collection/exhibitions/watercolours-and-drawings-in-the-collection-of-queen-elizabeth-the-queen/the-chelsea-royal-hospital-infirmery-as-destroyed-by-enemy-action>.

Bull, Norma. *The Circus, Bath*. 1942–43. Drawing in pencil, watercolour. 33.2 x 53.2 cm. National Gallery of Australia, Canberra, 84.1713, IRN 90657.
<https://searchthecollection.nga.gov.au/object/90657>.

Bull, Norma. *Coventry Cathedral 1943*. Ink and watercolour. 67.5 x 31.5 cm. Sold at auction by Bay East Auctions, Sydney, Australia.
<https://www.invaluable.com/auction-lot/norma-bull-1906-1980-coventry-cathedral-1943-wate-291-c-54d96d4e01>.

Bull, Norma. *Effigies of Crusaders in Round Temple Church, London: after Damage Enemy Action*. n.d. Watercolour. 42.6 x 57.5 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 4899.
<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/3817>.

Bull, Norma. *Exeter Cathedral: Temporary Repairs*. 1943. Drawing in pencil, pen, ink with watercolour. 57.8 x 44.6 cm. National Gallery of Australia, Canberra, 84.1715, IRN 90661.
<https://searchthecollection.nga.gov.au/object/90661>.

Bull, Norma. *Rocket Bomb Exploding in the Air over London*. 1945. Drawing, watercolour. Royal Collection Trust, RCIN 45376.
<https://www.rct.uk/collection/exhibitions/watercolours-and-drawings-in-the-collection-of-queen-elizabeth-the-queen/rocket-bomb-exploding-in-the-air-over-london>.

Bull, Norma. *Ruins in Central Exeter caused by Baedeker Raids*. 1943. Drawing in pen, black ink with watercolour. 38.8 x 52.7 cm. National Gallery of Australia, Canberra, 84.1714, IRN 90659.
<https://searchthecollection.nga.gov.au/object/90659>.

Bull, Norma. *St Giles, City of London*. c. 1943. Drawing in pencil, watercolour. 22.8 x 17.8 cm. National Gallery of Australia, Canberra, 84.1712, IRN 90655.
<https://searchthecollection.nga.gov.au/object/90655>.

Bull, Norma. *St. Paul's Cathedral on Victory Night, 8 May 1945*. 1945. Preparatory sketch, watercolour. Royal Collection Trust, RCIN 453417.
<https://www.rct.uk/collection/exhibitions/watercolours-and-drawings-in-the-collection-of-queen-elizabeth-the-queen/st-pauls-cathedral-on-victory-night>.

Bull, Norma. *St Thomas Church among the Ruins*. 1941. Drawing in pencil, pen, ink, watercolour. 57 x 39.2 cm. National Gallery of Australia, Canberra, 84.1716, IRN 90663.
<https://searchthecollection.nga.gov.au/object/90663>.
This probably depicts St Thomas the Martyr, in Bristol.

Bull, Norma. *Wings for Victory*. c. 1943. Pen and ink with watercolour. 42 x 58 cm. Castlemaine Art Museum, Castlemaine, Australia, G622.

<https://collection.castlemaineartmuseum.org.au/objects/622/wings-for-victory>.

Carr, Henry Marvell. *In the Temple Garden*. 1942. Oil on canvas. 76.5 x 102 cm. Royal Courts of Justice, The Strand (location), part of the Government Art Collection, London, 127.

<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/in-the-temple-garden-29844>.

Carr, Henry Marvell. *St. Clement Danes Church on Fire after being Bombed*. 1941. Oil on canvas. 76.2 x 91.4 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 1315.

<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/4592>.

Clause, William Lionel. *Civil Defence Day – 15th November 1942: At the South Door of St Paul's Cathedral*. 1943. Watercolour on paper. 58 x 93.2 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 2864.

<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/5138>.

Clause, William Lionel. *A Fire Guard Team, Exeter, 1943*. 1943. Oil on canvas. 64.1 x 76.2 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 3175.

<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/5139>.

Clause, William Lionel. *Study for 'A Fire Guard Team, Exeter.'* 1943. Watercolour, ink. 34.8 x 41 cm. Imperial War Museum, London, Art.IWM ART LD 3197.

<https://www.iwm.org.uk/collections/item/object/5140>.

Clilverd, Graham. *Regina Hotel after the Blitz*. In *Repairing War Torn Bath*. Bath: Bath Preservation Trust, 2005, figure 17. Catalogue for an exhibition at the Bath Preservation Trust, Bath, 1 – 25 November 2005.

<https://museumofbatharchitecture.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/4e.2-Reparing-War-Torn-Bath-2005.pdf>.

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St. Paul's through Bow Church Window. 1942. Watercolour. [Frontispiece]

The House of Commons. 1942. Drawing. [1]

St. Paul's and the Church of St. Vedast. 1944. Drawing. [2]

St. Clement Danes. 1941. Drawing. [3]

St. Dunstan's in the East. 1941. [4]

St. Alban's Wood Street. 1943. Drawing. [5]

St. Bride's. 1943. Drawing. [6]

St. Paul's from the East. 1941. Drawing. [7]

Pump Court. 1941. Watercolour. [8]

Near Goldsmith's Hall. 1943. Drawing. [9]

Guildhall. 1942. Drawing. [10]

All Hallows Barking-in-the-Tower. 1944. Drawing. [11]

In Red Lion Square. 1943. Drawing. [12]

Gray's Inn. 1941. Drawing. [13]

The Dutch Church, Austin Friars. 1942. Drawing. [14]

The Chapel of the Charterhouse. n.d. Drawing. [15]

St. Giles Cripplegate. 1944. Drawing. [16]

The Royal College of Surgeons. 1943. Drawing. [17]

St. Paul's from Queen Victoria Street. 1942. Watercolour. [18]

Christ Church Newgate Street. 1942. Drawing. [19]

St. Anne's Soho. 1942. Drawing. [20]

Ludgate Hill. 1942. Drawing. [21]

Cheapside. 1941. Drawing. [22]

St. James's Piccadilly. 1943. Drawing. [23]

In the City Ruins. 1943. Drawing. [24]

The Record Office. 1942. Drawing. [25]

St. Paul's from Dorset Rise. 1942. Drawing. [26]

St. Michael's Paternoster Royal. 1944. Drawing. [27]

St. Olave's Hart Street. 1943. Drawing. [28]

Guy's Hospital. 1945. Drawing. [29]

Charterhouse. 1942. Watercolour. [30]

St. Paul's from Paternoster Row. 1941. Drawing. [31]

The Inner Temple Library. 1942. Drawing. [32]

Water Gate, Essex Street. 1943. Drawing. [33]

St. Nicholas Cole Abbey. 1941. Drawing. [34]

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This scene was probably inspired by Hamburg, Germany.

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